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Article in *Agrochimica -Pisa-* · July 2015

DOI: 10.12871/0021857201534

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Production of cellulolytic and xylanolytic enzymes by fungi grown on cactus (nopal) in solid-state fermentation

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Received 14 June 2015 - Received in revised form 10 September 2015 - Accepted 11 September 2015

Keywords: cellulase, solid fermentation, *Trametes polyzona*, *Trichoderma harzianum*, xylanase

SUMMARY. – The main aim of this research was to describe the production of cellulase and xylanase enzymes by *Trichoderma harzianum* (ascomycete) and *Trametes polyzona* (basidiomycete) by solid-state fermentation using vegetable nopal and prickly pear paddle as substrates. Enzymatic activities were determined by reducing sugars quantification using the 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid method. For *T. harzianum*, the xylanase enzyme activity increased on vegetable nopal paddle with 2.34 U/g ds (gram of dry sample) on the 5th day of fermentation, while the prickly pear paddle turned out to be a better substrate for the cellulase activity with 0.57 U/g ds at the 3rd. day. For *T. polyzona*, the activity of both enzymes increased and the highest activity was yield on the 5th day of fermentation on vegetable nopal paddle, with values of 4.38 U/g ds for xylanase and 1.00 U/g ds for cellulase. Thus, it was possible to use this fungus in order to hydrolyze residues of nopal by solid state fermentation.

INTRODUCTION. – Solid-state fermentation is a technique frequently used for re-manufacturing products and to reduce contamination due to its advantage to use agricultural wastes as substrates. The agricultural wastes normally still contain untapped functional components with potential for development of new high value products (SAVAL, 2012).

According to SAGARPA (Ministry of Agriculture), in Mexico 760,000 tons of nopal are produced annually, 160,000 tons corresponding to agricultural residues. Nopal (cactus) wastes generally are accumulated

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Contribution presented at the workshop “Frontiers in Food Science for Feeding the World”, Department of Agriculture, Food and Environment, Pisa, 15 June 2015.

around in the environment, causing a serious pollution problem (SÁENZ *et al.*, 2006).

The main feature of vegetal wastes (like nopal) is their content of organic material like cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin (CUERVO *et al.*, 2009). Different processes have been development for converting agricultural residues into products with high commercial value. Bioprocess is a tool for obtaining low cost alternatives substrate, and to reduce contamination problems (OLIVEIRA *et al.*, 2006). The solid-state fermentation is a technique for improving the use of agricultural residues using microorganisms in low water contents. Solid-state fermentation has the advantage of conversion using agro-industrial residues as substrates which are converted in secondary metabolites such as organic acids, pesticides, aromatic compounds, fuels, cellulase and xylanase enzymes (BOTELLA *et al.*, 2005; SAVAL, 2012).

Cellulase is the general term for a group of enzymes consisting of endo-1,4- β -D-glucanase (EC 3.2.1.4), exo-1,4- β -glucanase (EC 3.2.1.91) and β -D-glucosidase (EC 3.2.1.21), and are commonly used in textile industry (BOTELLA *et al.*, 2005). The interest in using cellulase and xylanase began about the 50's, due to their potential for converting biomass to glucose and other soluble sugars. Moreover, in the textile industry (biostoning process and biopolishing) the enzymes are used to give the appearance of decolored in clothing; in paper industry in order to bleach pulps, and in food industry for juice extraction of vegetable and fruits, filtration of musts, and comestible oils extraction. Indeed, enzymes are using for partial hydrolysis of lignocellulose materials for improve digestion in ruminants (ARGUMEDO *et al.*, 2009).

Fungi ascomycetes are widely used in many industrial applications because of their high capacity to degrade cellulose and hemicellulose. One of the genera mostly recognized is *Trichoderma*. Concerning the lignocellulolytic basidiomycetous fungi, also called white-rot fungus, they are able to colonize and degrade lignocellulose materials, and are characterized for having a ligninolytic oxidative system widely developed; additionally, they display a system for hydrolases production. *Trametes* is one of the most recognized and extensively investigated genera as well (GARCÍA and SÁENZ, 2003; COSTA *et al.*, 2010). Thus, the aim of this work was the production of xylanase and cellulase enzymes by *Trichoderma harzianum* and *Trametes polyzona* in solid-state fermentation, using as substrate two agro-industrial residues: vegetable nopal and fruit nopal.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. – Agricultural wastes. – Nopal paddles (cactus) were collected from two different regions of Mexico during March 2014: nopal for consumption as vegetable (vegetable nopal) from Cuautlacingo, and nopal for fruit production (fruit nopal) from Tlalmimilolpa. Nopal is considered as an agricultural waste because of the lack of quality characteristics for the consumers such as correct size, shape and color.

Proximate composition. – Protein (total nitrogen), fat, crude fiber and ash analyses were performed on nopal wastes according to AOAC (Association of Official Agricultural Chemists) official methods. Cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin concentrations were determined by the detergent method as described by VAN SOEST (1991).

Pretreatment of nopal wastes. – Nopal paddles were thoroughly washed and sanitized, excess water was removed and then they were maintained at room temperature to allow drain. Nopal wastes were milled and the particle size was homogenized at 0.841-1.19 mm. Afterwards, samples were washing with hot water (80°C), and oven-dried at 45°C for 24 h. Finally, assay tubes with 1 g of nopal wastes were autoclaved (121°C for 15 min) for use in the experiments.

Inoculum medium. – *Trichoderma harzianum* was growth at 28°C for seven days on potato dextrose agar (PDA) (Bioxon) to allow spore formation. Spores were washed from agar of 7-days with 15 mL of sterile distilled water; spores were counted using a Neubauer chamber, and 1×10^7 spores/g were added to Pontecorvo medium. Pontecorvo medium was prepared mixing 6 g NaNO_3 , 1.52 g KH_2PO_4 , 0.52 g KCl, 0.52 g $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1.0 g yeast extract in 1 L of distilled water at pH 6.5. *Trametes polyzona* was growth on PDA at 28°C for five days. Thereafter, slices of 1 cm^2 from mycelium were added to flasks with Pontecorvo medium and incubated at 28°C and centrifuged at 180 rpm for 24 h to allow mycelium separation from the agar.

Solid-state fermentation. – Nopal wastes (vegetable nopal and fruit nopal) were used as the sole nutrient source for solid-state fermentation. To each assay tube, one gram of these samples was previously sterilized. Spore suspension of *Trichoderma harzianum* or mycelium suspension of *Trametes polyzona* were inoculated to each assay tube until 80% moisture. Assay tubes *Trametes polyzona* were maintained at 28°C for 10 days, and *Trichoderma harzianum* for 8 days at the same temperature. Sampling was performed in triplicate every 24 h.

Enzyme extraction. – Crude enzyme was extracted by mixing 1 g of fermented matter with 5 mL distilled water on a vortex for 3 min.

The suspension was then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 5 min, and the supernatant was designated as crude extract.

Enzyme assays. – Xylan (Sigma) was used as substrate in order to determine the xylanase activity; a xylose standard curve was used. Carboxymethylcellulose (Sigma, low viscosity) was used as substrate to determine the carboxymethylcellulase activity; a glucose standard curve was used. The reducing sugars quantification was performed with the 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (Sigma) method (MILLER, 1959) as an indirect measure of production. Briefly, the reaction mixture was heated in a boiling water bath for 10 min. The absorbance of reactions at room temperature was measured at 640 nm. One unit (U) of enzyme activity is defined as the amount of enzyme required to release one μmol of reducing sugar (xylose and glucose, respectively) per min under standard assay conditions. The xylanolytic and cellulolytic activities are expressed as U/g ds (gram dry sample).

Statistical analysis. – Experiments were performed in triplicate; results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Data were analyzed by ANOVA using t-student and Tukey tests to compare groups and control data with significance level of 95% ($P < 0.05$) using the Minitab 17 software (USA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. – In this work, a bioprocess was used in order to produce enzymes with industrial applications. Filamentous fungi were used due to their natural ability to colonize and degrade lignocellulosic wastes like nopal. The proximate composition results from vegetable nopal and fruit nopal are shown in Table 1. Protein and ash contents were significantly different for both wastes ($P < 0.05$), while between the fat and crude fiber content there was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$). Crude fiber content was 16.67 g/100 g for vegetable

TABLE 1. – *Proximate composition of vegetable nopal and fruit nopal paddles (g/100 g dry weight).*

Component	Vegetable nopal	Fruit nopal
Protein	18.68 \pm 0.46 ^A	8.80 \pm 0.19 ^B
Fat	2.17 \pm 0.28 ^A	1.39 \pm 0.16 ^A
Ash	19.95 \pm 0.89 ^A	15.16 \pm 0.37 ^B
Crude fiber	16.67 \pm 1.43 ^A	15.07 \pm 0.60 ^A

Values are expressed as means ($n=3$) \pm standard deviation. In rows values with the same capital letter are significantly different ($P < 0.05$).

nopal and 15.07 g/100 g for fruit nopal. These results are in accordance with GEBREMARIAM *et al.* (2006) who reported about 11-15% crude fiber content for several *Opuntia* (cactus) species. One of the principal components in fiber are cellulose and hemicellulose, therefore the nopal wastes analyzed were a suitable substrate for their use in solid-state fermentation.

Table 2 shows the content of different lignocellulose fractions from vegetable nopal and fruit nopal paddles. For both paddles, hemicellulose was the component with the highest level, followed by cellulose and lignin. Hemicellulose and cellulose contents from vegetable nopal paddles were significantly different ($P < 0.05$), vegetable nopal paddles contained high proportion of these polysaccharides.

Due to the complex and heterogeneous structure of cellulose, fungi require a complex enzyme system for their degradation, in which cellulases and xylanases hydrolytic enzymes work together. We worked with two fungi strains, the ascomycete *Trichoderma harzianum* and the basidiomycete *Trametes polyzona*. After solid-state fermentation, cellulase and xylanase activities in crude extracts were performed. PAREDES *et al.* (2010) mentioned that enzyme activity is an appropriated method to determinate the enzyme concentration during solid-state fermentation.

Enzyme activities were detected for *Trichoderma harzianum* and *Trametes polyzona* when vegetable nopal and fruit nopal wastes were used as substrates. The xylanase enzyme profile produced by *T. harzianum* is shown in Fig. 1. A similar production was appreciated in the first two days for both wastes. From the 3rd day xylanase production was improved, and after 5 days a significantly difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in xylanase concentrations for vegetable nopal with 2.34 U/g ds compared to fruit nopal, in which the maximum production was found

TABLE 2. – Concentration of lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose in nopal paddles (g/100 g dry weight).

Sample	Vegetable nopal	Fruit nopal
Hemicellulose	15.13 ± 0.49 ^A	11.24 ± 0.28 ^B
Cellulose	12.24 ± 0.29 ^A	10.20 ± 0.33 ^B
Lignin	3.68 ± 0.33 ^A	4.29 ± 0.39 ^A

Values are expressed as means ($n=3$) ± standard deviation. In rows values with the same capital letter are significantly different ($P < 0.05$).

FIG. 1. – Xylanase activity of *T. harzianum* during solid-state fermentation with nopal paddles as substrate. Error bars are the standard deviation of the mean ($n=3$).

at day 6 with 1.10 U/g ds. After the maximum production (days 5 and 6, respectively), the enzyme concentrations decreased. These results are in agreement with a previous study (SALGADO *et al.*, 2014) which reported 0.02-3.06 U/g ds xylanase activity in two different industrial wastes: wine and olive oil (single or mixed) using *Aspergillus niger*, a fungi strain widely used for enzyme production at industrial scale.

For cellulase production by *T. harzianum* (Fig. 2), an early production of cellulase was observed after 24 h in fruit nopal wastes, indicating the affinity of *T. harzianum* for this agricultural waste; the maximum production (0.57 U/g ds) was achieved at day 3. In case of vegetable nopal wastes, the cellulase production (0.31 U/g ds) was significantly lower ($P<0.05$). After these maximum picks, the activities diminished.

The ascomycetes more employed for commercial production of cellulase are *Trichoderma* and *Aspergillus* genera (SALGADO *et al.*, 2014). Our results are similar to the ones reported by LIO and WANG (2012), with values of cellulase activity ranging from 0.4 to 1.2 U/g ds when corn and soybean wastes were used as substrates by *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Trichoderma reesei* and *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* in solid-state fermentation. SALGADO *et al.* (2014) detected an enzyme activity of about 0.08-5.2 U/g ds by *Aspergillus niger* using wine and oil olive wastes (single and/or mixed) as substrates.

FIG. 2. – Cellulase activity of *T. harzianum* during solid-state fermentation with nopal paddles as substrate. Error bars are the standard deviation of the mean ($n=3$).

The profile production of xylanases by *T. polyzona* is described in Fig. 3. There was no significant difference ($P>0.05$) after 4 days in enzyme activity for both substrates. The maximum activity of xylanase (4.38 U/g ds) was found at day 5 for vegetable nopal, while fruit nopal paddles exhibited their maximum value (3.6 U/g ds) at day 6. There was no significance difference ($P>0.05$) comparing the maximum xylanase activity for both substrates. However, we considered the vegetable nopal as a better substrate because enzyme activity was detected faster than fruit nopal. Similarly, *Trametes versicolor* grown on corn straw with different percentages of humidity, resulted in a xylanase activity of about 0.66-8.25 U/g ds (ZHU *et al.*, 2013). Another study reported that *Pleurotus ostreatus* (a basidiomycete widely used in enzymes production) displayed about 0.98-5.79 U/g ds xylanase activity (MEMBRILLO *et al.*, 2008), similarly to the data found in this work.

In the case of cellulase production by *T. polyzona*, in the first days of fermentation we observed a similarly behavior (Fig. 4) of xylanase activity. The cellulase activity increased up to day 4, and the highest cellulase activity (0.91 U/g ds) was found after 5 days of fermentation for vegetable nopal paddles. In fruit nopal paddles substrate the maximum cellulase activity (1.0 U/g ds) was found at 8-day fermentation. After these

FIG. 3. – Xylanase activity of *T. polyzona* during solid-state fermentation with nopal paddles as substrate. Error bars are the standard deviation of the mean ($n=3$).

FIG. 4. – Cellulase activity of *T. polyzona* during solid-state fermentation with nopal paddles as substrate. Error bars are the standard deviation of the mean ($n=3$).

time-points, the activity started to decrease. Despite these values, there was no significantly difference ($P>0.05$). Nopal consumable as vegetable could be considered better than nopal fruit substrate due to the enzyme

activity detected firstly. Experimental results are closely related to those reported by PAREDES *et al.* (2010) for cellulase production by *Pleurotus ostreatus* and *P. pulmonarius* using leaves of banana as solid substrate (1.96 and 1.78 U/g ds, respectively). MÁRQUEZ *et al.* (2007) also reported a similar range (1.16 U/g ds) for *P. ostreatus* grown on sugar cane bagasse.

Low levels of activity in the initial step of incubation could represent basal constitutive levels of the enzymes. Enzyme synthesis increased during the fermentation time demonstrating their activity on nopal wastes. This behavior has been observed in various studies (SOLIMAN *et al.*, 2012; SALGADO *et al.*, 2014; Lio and WANG, 2012; ZHU *et al.*, 2013). Experimental results indicate that there is a higher xylanase activity than cellulase activity for both fungi as well as for both substrates, and this may be related to the greater amount of hemicellulose than cellulose present in nopal wastes.

Since culture conditions for enzyme production are affected by the type of carbon source and incubation time, the selection of an appropriate substrate is very important for successful xylanase and cellulase production. Substrates do not have the unique function as carbon source, but they also have other important characteristics for better enzyme production by microorganism. Additionally, the time incubation for achieving cellulase enzyme production depend on different factors as size and surface of the fibrils, the space between the microfibrils and cellulose molecules in the amorphous regions, the crystallinity degree of the cellulose, the stereoscopic shape and stiffness of cellulosic units, their origin (nature), concentration and distribution of substituent groups (AHMED *et al.*, 2009). Meanwhile, xylanase activity depends on the source of hemicellulose, size and surface of fibrils, and degradability of the carbon source (SONIA *et al.*, 2005). On the other hand, agricultural wastes are abundant in the world and their treatment is important to avoid pollution. The solid-state fermentation offers a clear advantage to converted these wastes into secondary metabolites like enzymes, obtaining a higher product yield at low production costs (SANGHVI *et al.* 2010).

This is the first time that nopal paddle wastes were investigated as possible substrates for enzyme production using solid-state fermentation. According to the results presented, the nopal wastes are viable and have potential to be used as substrates to obtain new high value products. Therefore, on the basis of our analyses the best combination of strains and substrates (four combinations) to produce both enzymes were *Trametes polyzona* strain and vegetable nopal as substrate.

CONCLUSIONS. – Solid-state fermentation is an efficient and economical system for producing hydrolytic enzymes without expensive equipment. In this work, we demonstrated that nopal wastes have important components to allow their use as substrates for the production of cellulases and xylanases by *Trametes polyzona*. The increasing activities of xylanases and cellulases presented at day 5 of fermentation allow to consider *Trametes polyzona* as potential enzyme-producing fungus, with possible commercial application. Finally, is important to continue searching others microorganisms with biotechnological potential.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS. – This study was funded by the Nacional Polytechnic Institute by SIP 20150080. MESP and AOM are members of SNI and have institutional grants (COFAA and EDI). Master studies of AGMR have been supported by CONACyT Mexico (fellow 584173). The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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